

1 **Supplementary Material**

2 **“DI_{cle}, a Measure Consisting of Insulin Sensitivity, Secretion, and Clearance, Captures**
3 **Differences Between Diabetic and Nondiabetic States”**

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11 **Appendix**

12 **1. Validity of Eq (3), the equation relating insulin sensitivity, insulin secretion, insulin** 13 **clearance, and blood glucose levels**

14 To further validate Eq (3), we investigated the equations in which the coefficient of k_7 is 1 or
15 3 (Fig. S2). The r value of Eq (3) for the NGT, IGT, and T2DM groups was better than that
16 of the equations in which the coefficient of k_7 is 1 or 3. Differences in the parameters of Eq
17 (3) among NGT, IGT, and T2DM groups were smaller compared with those for the equations
18 in which the coefficient of k_7 is 1 or 3 (Fig. S2), suggesting that Eq (3), whose coefficient of
19 k_7 is 2, provides the best representation of blood glucose levels. To further investigate the
20 goodness-of-fit of the equations in individuals with each category of glucose tolerance, we
21 also conducted standardized major axis tests (Fig. S3), which have been used to investigate
22 relationships among variables (1,2). The estimated coefficients of Eq (2) were statistically
23 significantly different among NGT, IGT, and T2DM groups (Fig. S3A), but the differences in
24 the estimated coefficients of Eq (3) were relatively small (Fig. S3B), indicating that Eq (3)
25 provides a better representation of blood glucose levels than does Eq (2) for NGT, IGT, and
26 T2DM groups.

27 We also estimated insulin secretion from the serum C-peptide concentrations, as
28 previously described (3). As an index of insulin secretion (k_{sec}), we calculated the insulin
29 secretion rate at the fasting state (3) divided by the fasting glucose level. As an index of
30 insulin sensitivity (k_{sen}), we calculated insulin sensitivity index (ISI) (4). As an index of
31 insulin clearance (k_{cle}), we calculated metabolic clearance rate (MCR) (4,5). Of note, these
32 parameters were estimated from a hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic clamp alone. Even when
33 insulin sensitivity, insulin secretion, and insulin clearance were estimated in this way, Eq (3)
34 provided a better representation of blood glucose levels than does Eq (2) (Fig. S4).

35 Instead of k_{sec} , we also investigated the first-phase insulin secretion (k_{sf}). Even with
36 this first-phase insulin secretion, Eq (3) tended to show a better fit than Eq (2): the r value of

Eq (2) for the NGT, IGT, and T2DM groups was 0.06 (95% CI, -0.17 to 0.30), 0.08 (95% CI, -0.49 to 0.47), and 0.42 (95% CI, 0.02 to 0.61), respectively, and the r value of Eq (3) for the NGT, IGT, and T2DM groups was 0.53 (95% CI, 0.28 to 0.71), 0.38 (95% CI, -0.08 to 0.71), and 0.35 (95% CI, 0.09 to 0.58), respectively. However, when insulin secretion was calculated in this way, the equation in which the coefficient of insulin clearance is 1 also showed a good fit: the r value of the equation in which the coefficient of insulin clearance is 1 for the NGT, IGT, and T2DM groups was 0.53 (95% CI, 0.28 to 0.71), 0.37 (95% CI, -0.11 to 0.73), and 0.41 (95% CI, 0.11 to 0.61), respectively. This result may be because the dimension of insulin secretion differs depending on the calculation methods, as we discussed in Appendix 2. Either way, these results indicate the need to consider not only insulin secretion and insulin sensitivity but also insulin clearance to represent blood glucose levels, especially in NGT and IGT groups.

49

50 **2. Relation between “ DI_{cle} ” and “basal insulin effect”**

51 This appendix details how “ DI_{cle} ” can be approximated as the extension of basal insulin
 52 effect (BIE) (6) to the insulin effect during glucose administration. BIE is the effect of basal
 53 insulin on glucose uptake, and defined as follows (6):

$$54 \quad \text{BIE} = I_{\text{basal}}k_{\text{sen}}, \quad \text{Eq (5)}$$

55 where I_{basal} and k_{sen} are the basal insulin concentration and insulin sensitivity, respectively.

56 We extended the concept of BIE to a steady state insulin effect (SIE) during glucose
 57 administration as follows:

$$58 \quad \text{SIE} = I_{\text{SS}}k_{\text{sen}}, \quad \text{Eq (6)}$$

59 where I_{SS} is the insulin concentration at the steady state. The minimal model, a mostly used
 60 mathematical model of glucose, cannot admit an equilibrium and, in some conditions, the
 61 concentration of insulin increases without bounds (7). Using a modified simple, stable, and
 62 unified model (7), I_{SS} can be transformed as follows:

63
$$I_{SS} = G_{SS} \frac{k_{sec}}{k_{cle}}, \quad \text{Eq (7)}$$

64 where G_{SS} , k_{sec} , and k_{cle} are the glucose concentration at the steady state, insulin secretion,
65 and insulin clearance, respectively.

66 Blood glucose levels after glucose administration (G) are experimentally
67 approximated only by insulin clearance, as follows (4):

68
$$G \propto \frac{1}{k_{cle}}. \quad \text{Eq (8)}$$

69 Eq (6), (7), and (8) can be transformed and approximated as follows:

70
$$\text{SIE} \propto \frac{k_{sen}k_{sec}}{k_{cle}^2}. \quad \text{Eq (9)}$$

71 The right side of Eq (9) is the same as the combination of the insulin-related indices
72 on the right side of Eq (4), suggesting that DI_{cle} can be approximated as the extension of BIE
73 to the insulin effect during glucose administration. The dimension of SIE is dL/mg, which is
74 the same as the dimension of $1/G$. Hence, it is plausible that SIE is inversely correlated with
75 blood glucose levels. Of note, the dimension of k_{sec} in Eq (9) is 1/min, but if k_{sec} is
76 calculated based on first-phase insulin secretion, the dimension of k_{sec} becomes 1. Therefore,
77 when assessing DI_{cle} based on first-phase insulin secretion, the dimension of $k_{sen}k_{sec}/k_{cle}$ is
78 dL/mg. This is consistent with the results shown in Appendix 1, and it is essential to consider
79 the dimension of each parameter when determining the coefficients of DI_{cle} .

80

81 **3. DI_{cle} and glucose effectiveness determine blood glucose levels**

82 This appendix details how blood glucose levels are determined by DI_{cle} and glucose
83 effectiveness. We examined a steady state during glucose administration by using a simple
84 and stable model (7), which can be written as follows:

85
$$0 = -k_{glu}G - k_{sen}IG + f, \quad \text{Eq (10)}$$

86
$$0 = k_{sec}G - k_{cle}I, \quad \text{Eq (11)}$$

87 where G and I indicate blood glucose and insulin levels, respectively. The indices k_{glu} , k_{sen} ,
 88 k_{sec} and k_{cle} are glucose effectiveness, insulin sensitivity, insulin secretion, and insulin
 89 clearance, respectively. f is the sum of the constant baseline hepatic glucose release and the
 90 amount of infused glucose.

91 Eq (10) and Eq (11) can be transformed as follows:

$$92 \quad f = \frac{k_{\text{sen}}k_{\text{sec}}}{k_{\text{cle}}}G^2 + k_{\text{glu}}G. \quad \text{Eq (12)}$$

93 Hence, the effect of insulin on blood glucose levels may be $k_{\text{sen}}k_{\text{sec}}/k_{\text{cle}}$, taking glucose
 94 effectiveness into account. However, glucose effectiveness cannot be evaluated precisely by
 95 using this kind of simple one-compartment model (8). Further studies investigating the effect
 96 of insulin and glucose effectiveness on blood glucose levels are warranted.

97 One possible explanation for the difference between $\text{DI}_{/\text{cle}}$ defined in this study
 98 ($k_{\text{sen}}k_{\text{sec}}/k_{\text{cle}}^2$) and the analytically indicated insulin effect ($k_{\text{sen}}k_{\text{sec}}/k_{\text{cle}}$) is that the effect
 99 of insulin may depend on blood glucose levels, as shown in Appendix 2 (*i.e.*, even if insulin
 100 sensitivity, insulin secretion, and insulin clearance are the same, higher blood glucose levels
 101 can increase the insulin effect to lower blood glucose levels). Eq (12) can be transformed as
 102 follows:

$$103 \quad G = \frac{f}{\frac{k_{\text{sen}}k_{\text{sec}}}{k_{\text{cle}}}G + k_{\text{glu}}}. \quad \text{Eq (13)}$$

104 Blood glucose levels are affected not only by insulin sensitivity, insulin secretion, and insulin
 105 clearance, but also by glucose effectiveness; however, if blood glucose levels are
 106 approximated only by insulin clearance, Eq (8) can be experimentally indicated. Taken
 107 together, Eq (13) can be approximated and transformed as follows:

$$108 \quad G \sim \frac{f}{\frac{k_{\text{sen}}k_{\text{sec}}}{k_{\text{cle}}^2}k + k_{\text{glu}}}, \quad \text{Eq (14)}$$

109 where k is the weight of DI_{cle} ($k_{sen}k_{sec}/k_{cle}^2$) relative to glucose effectiveness (k_{glu}) in
 110 controlling blood glucose levels. Hence, blood glucose levels during glucose administration
 111 are mainly determined by DI_{cle} ($k_{sen}k_{sec}/k_{cle}^2$) and glucose effectiveness (k_{glu}).

112

113 **4. Relation between the phenomenon of “moving up the curve” of DI_{cle} and a pathway** 114 **of glucose homeostasis failure predicted by a previous modeling study**

115 This appendix indicates that the phenomenon of “moving up the curve” of DI_{cle} for IGT (Fig.
 116 2) represents almost the same phenomenon as predicted in the previous modeling study (9),
 117 indicating a pathway to failure of glucose homeostasis in which a change in insulin clearance
 118 alter glucose dynamics even when the normal glucose set point is maintained.

119 Glucose homeostasis is reported to show “dynamical compensation”, a property of
 120 systems in which for every time varying input, the complete dynamics of the output are
 121 insensitive to variations in key parameters of the system (9). The glucose homeostasis circuit,
 122 which represents dynamical compensation, can be written as follows:

$$123 \quad \frac{dG}{dt} = u_0 + u(t) - (k_{glu} + k_{sen}I)G, \quad \text{Eq (15)}$$

$$124 \quad \frac{dI}{dt} = p\beta \cdot \rho(G) - k_{cle}I, \quad \text{Eq (16)}$$

$$125 \quad \frac{d\beta}{dt} = \beta \cdot h(G), \quad \text{Eq (17)}$$

126 where u_0 and $u(t)$ are endogenous glucose production and infused glucose, respectively, p
 127 and β represent insulin secretion and beta-cell functional mass, respectively, and $\rho(G)$ is a
 128 monotonically increasing function of G . $h(G)$ is the beta-cell growth rate, and at the glucose
 129 set point, $G = G_0$, $h(G_0) = 0$. This system was reported to have dynamical compensation
 130 with respect to insulin sensitivity, k_{sen} . Of note, k_{cle} includes both peripheral and hepatic
 131 insulin clearance, since insulin recirculates to the liver through hepatic vein and artery (10).

132 As previously described (9), the steady-state solution can be written as follows:

133
$$\frac{k_{\text{sen}} p \beta \cdot \rho(G_0)}{k_{\text{cle}}} = \text{constant} \quad \text{Eq (18)}$$

134 which can be approximated as the analytically indicated DI_{cle} is constant (Appendix 2).

135 The previous study (9) showed that this model does not have dynamical
136 compensation to variation in insulin clearance, and that the change in insulin clearance alter
137 glucose dynamics even when the normal glucose set point G_0 is maintained. This can be
138 considered as a pathway for progression of glucose intolerance (9). The decrease in insulin
139 clearance with maintained G_0 and with satisfying Eq (18) represent almost the same
140 phenomenon of “moving up the hyperbolic curve” of DI_{cle} . Hence, the phenomenon of
141 “moving up the curve” of DI_{cle} at the early stage of glucose intolerance can be considered as
142 the same phenomenon that the change in insulin clearance alter glucose dynamics even when
143 the normal glucose set point is maintained.

144 There are several different methods for calculating DI, some of which are based on
145 the product of insulin concentration and insulin sensitivity (11). However, this result
146 indicated that an increase in insulin concentration due to increased insulin secretion and an
147 increase in insulin concentration due to decreased insulin clearance may have different effects
148 on glucose dynamics.

149 It may seem contradictory that while DI_{cle} well correlated with PG120, DI_{cle} was
150 comparable between NGT and IGT. One possible explanation for this is that blood glucose
151 fluctuations can be changed even with the same DI_{cle} , as we described in this Appendix.
152 Another possible explanation for this is that other kind of regulatory mechanisms such as
153 glucose effectiveness and the effect of glucagon are related to the glucose intolerance (12,13).
154 The other possible explanation is that there may actually be a difference in DI_{cle} between
155 NGT and IGT because there were not enough participants to capture the statistically
156 significant difference in DI_{cle} between NGT and IGT. Although DI_{cle} did not differ
157 significantly between NGT and IGT, this does not mean that it was clinically equivalent in

158 the two groups. Given our previous finding that k_7 , a parameter for insulin clearance, was
159 significantly reduced in individuals with IGT relative to those with NGT (4), however, the
160 decline in DI_{cle} is not as great as that in DI in the progression from NGT to IGT. Hence, Eq
161 (4) needs to be improved and validated in the future to reflect blood glucose fluctuations
162 more accurately.

163

164 **5, Previously reported mathematical model cannot estimate DI_{cle} from a** 165 **hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic clamp alone**

166 For each of the 112 subjects, we estimated the parameters of the previously reported
167 mathematical model (4) (Fig S6A) to reproduce the time course of the hyperinsulinemic-
168 euglycemic clamp. Some estimated parameters including k_{5_ins} and k_{7_ins} , which
169 correspond to insulin secretion and insulin clearance, respectively, showed a tendency to
170 diverge (*i.e.*, their value reached the predetermined upper or lower limits in some subjects)
171 (Fig. S6B). An estimated parameter, k_{4_ins} , which corresponds to insulin sensitivity
172 estimated from the hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic clamp alone, was statistically significantly
173 correlated with k_{4_full} , which corresponds to insulin sensitivity estimated from both
174 hyperglycemic and hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic clamps (Fig. S6C). However, k_{5_ins} ,
175 k_{7_ins} , and $k_{5}/k_{7}^2_{ins}$, which correspond to insulin secretion, insulin clearance, and the
176 ratio of insulin secretion to the square of insulin clearance estimated from the
177 hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic clamp alone, respectively, were not statistically significantly
178 correlated with k_{5_full} , k_{7_full} , and $k_{5}/k_{7}^2_{full}$, which correspond to insulin secretion,
179 insulin clearance, and the ratio of insulin secretion to the square of insulin clearance
180 estimated from both the hyperglycemic clamp and the hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic clamp
181 (Fig. S6C), respectively. Since insulin sensitivity and insulin clearance were reported to be
182 able to be calculated from the hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic clamp (10,14), if insulin

183 secretion or the ratio of insulin secretion to the square of insulin clearance can be estimated
 184 from the hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic clamp alone, DI_{cle} can be estimated from a single
 185 clamp test. Hence, we investigated whether insulin secretion or the ratio of insulin secretion
 186 to the square of insulin clearance could be estimated from the hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic
 187 clamp alone. Of note, it is neither a necessary nor a sufficient condition for estimating DI_{cle}
 188 that insulin secretion or the ratio of insulin secretion to the square of insulin clearance can be
 189 estimated from the hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic clamp alone; however, we examined these
 190 two to exclude the possibilities that only insulin sensitivity, which has been estimated only
 191 from the hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic clamp alone (4), can be estimated and that insulin
 192 secretion cannot be estimated at all.

193 Consequently, DI_{cle} estimated from the hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic clamp alone
 194 ($k_4 k_5 / k_7^2_{ins}$) was not statistically significantly correlated with DI_{cle} estimated from both
 195 the hyperglycemic clamp and the hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic clamp ($k_4 k_5 / k_7^2_{full}$) ($r =$
 196 0.11 ; 95% CI, -0.08 to 0.30) (Figs. S6C, S7A). We hypothesized that the reason for this
 197 result might be related to the model structure: in this model (Fig. S6A), glucose and insulin
 198 are injected around the pancreas (X and Y), but they are injected in the peripheral blood
 199 during the clamp test.

200

201 **6, Modified mathematical model**

202 We constructed a mathematical model of the feedback loop that links glucose and insulin
 203 (Fig. 3A) by modifying the previously reported model (4) with changing the position of
 204 influx G and influx I , and with the addition of k_{m8} as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{dG}{dt} &= \text{flux 1} - \text{flux 2} + \text{flux 3} - \text{flux 4} + \text{influx } G \\
 &= k_{m1}Y - k_{m2}G + \frac{k_{m3}}{k_{m8} + I} - k_{m4}GI + f_1(t)
 \end{aligned}$$

206

207
$$\frac{dI}{dt} = \text{flux 6} - \text{flux 7} + \text{influx } I = k_{m6}X - k_{m7}I + f_2(t)$$

208
$$\frac{dY}{dt} = -\text{flux 1} + \text{flux 2} = -k_{m1}Y + k_{m2}G$$

209
$$\frac{dX}{dt} = \text{flux 5} - \text{flux 6} = k_{m5}Y - k_{m6}X$$

210 where the variables G and I denote blood glucose and insulin concentrations, respectively.

211 The fluxes, influx G and influx I denote glucose and insulin infusions, respectively.

212 For each subject, the parameters of the model to reproduce the time course were
 213 estimated, as described previously (4,15). In brief, each parameter of the model for plasma
 214 glucose and serum insulin concentration was estimated in the range from 10^{-4} to 10^4 . For
 215 these methods, the parameters were estimated to minimize the objective function value. The
 216 value was defined as residual sum of the square (RSS) between the measured time course
 217 during the clamp analyses and the model trajectories. RSS used in the model was given by
 218 the following equation:

219
$$\text{RSS} = \frac{n_I}{n_G+n_I} \sum_{i=1}^{n_G} [G(t_i) - G_{\text{sim}}(t_i)]^2 + \frac{n_G}{n_G+n_I} \sum_{i=1}^{n_I} [I(t_i) - I_{\text{sim}}(t_i)]^2,$$

220 where n_G and n_I are the total numbers of time points of plasma glucose and serum insulin,
 221 respectively, t_i is the time of i -th time point. Plasma glucose and serum insulin
 222 concentrations of each subject were normalized by dividing them by the respective maximum
 223 value. $G(t)$ is the time-averaged plasma glucose level within the time range $(t - 5)$ min to t
 224 min. The interval was every 1-min. $I(t)$ is the serum insulin level at t min. $G_{\text{sim}}(t)$ and
 225 $I_{\text{sim}}(t)$ are simulated blood glucose and blood insulin levels, respectively. The numbers of
 226 generations and parents of the meta-evolutionary programming were 4000 and 400,
 227 respectively. Of note, identifiability of the parameters (16) of this model was not validated.
 228 Hence, even if DI_{cle} can be estimated at the population level, it may not be possible to
 229 uniquely identify all parameters in an individual.

230

231 **7. Prediction of DI_{cle} from a hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic clamp alone**

232 This appendix details how DI_{cle} was estimated from a hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic clamp
233 alone using a simple analytically computable method.

234 Following a formula for calculating insulin sensitivity index (ISI) (4), insulin
235 sensitivity (k_{sen}) can be approximated as follows:

$$236 \quad 0 = -k_{sen}I_{SS}G_{SS} + f_g, \quad \text{Eq (19)}$$

237 where I_{SS} , G_{SS} , and f_g represent blood insulin level at the steady state during a
238 hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic clamp, blood glucose level at the steady state during a
239 hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic clamp, and glucose infusion rate at the steady state,
240 respectively.

241 Eq (11) can be transformed as follows:

$$242 \quad \frac{k_{sec}}{k_{cle}} = \frac{I_0}{G_0}, \quad \text{Eq (20)}$$

243 where I_0 and G_0 represent blood insulin level in the fasting state and blood glucose level in
244 the fasting state, respectively.

245 Following a formula for calculating metabolic clearance rate (4,5), insulin clearance
246 (k_{cle}) can be approximated as follows:

$$247 \quad k_{cle} = \frac{f_i}{I_{SS} - I_0}, \quad \text{Eq (21)}$$

248 where f_i represents insulin infusion rate at the steady state. Of note, this method cannot
249 distinguish peripheral insulin clearance from hepatic insulin clearance (10). In addition, k_{cle}
250 in Eq (20) and that in Eq (21) can be different, and this method may cause some bias.

251 Eq (19), Eq (20) and Eq (21) can be transformed and approximated as follows:

$$252 \quad \frac{k_{sen}k_{sec}}{k_{cle}^2} \sim \frac{f_g I_0 (I_{SS} - I_0)}{f_i G_{SS} G_0 I_{SS}} \quad \text{Eq (22)}$$

253 Of note, since k_{cle} in Eq (20) and that in Eq (21) can be different, the values of both sides of
254 Eq (22) are not equal.

255

256 **8. Estimation of DI_{cle} from an oral glucose tolerance test or a fasting blood test**

257 This appendix details how DI_{cle} was estimated from OGTT or a fasting blood test. Here, as
258 an index of insulin secretion (k_{sec}), we calculated the insulin secretion rate at the fasting state
259 (3) divided by the fasting glucose level. As an index of insulin clearance (k_{sen}), we
260 calculated the insulin secretion rate at the fasting state (3) divided by the fasting insulin level,
261 as previously proposed (17). As an index of insulin sensitivity during OGTT (k_{sen_OGTT}), we
262 calculated oral glucose insulin sensitivity (OGIS) (18). It is worth noting that DI_{cle} calculated
263 with Matsuda index (19) was relatively weakly correlated with that calculated from two
264 clamp tests ($r = 0.28$; 95% CI, 0.09 to 0.45). We thus used OGIS in calculating DI_{cle} . As an
265 index of insulin sensitivity at the fasting state (k_{sen_fast}), we calculated insulin sensitivity
266 index (IS), which is the inverse of HOMA-IR (11). Of note, these insulin sensitivity-related
267 indices may differ as to whether they are influenced by total body, peripheral, or liver insulin
268 sensitivity, but since this has not yet been fully clarified (20), the present study examined the
269 predictive accuracy of DI_{cle} without considering the type of insulin sensitivity.

270 DI_{cle} estimated from OGTT ($k_{sen}k_{sec}/k_{cle}^2_{OGTT}$) and from a fasting blood test
271 ($k_{sen}k_{sec}/k_{cle}^2_{fast}$) were defined as $k_{sen_OGTT}k_{sec}/k_{cle}^2$ and $k_{sen_fast}k_{sec}/k_{cle}^2$,
272 respectively. Because systematic errors can occur depending on which method is used to
273 estimate DI_{cle} , we did not apply the Bland-Altman Analysis, but only examined the
274 correlations between each indicator.

275

278 **Figure S1. Relation among insulin-related parameters.**

279 (A) Scatter plot for $a \log k_7 + \log b$ versus $\log k_4 k_5$ (Eq (1)). Each point corresponds to the
280 values for a single subject. Green circles, red crosses, and blue squares indicate NGT, IGT,
281 and T2DM subjects, respectively. R^2 is the coefficient of determination, and the value in the
282 parenthesis is 95% confidence interval. The parameters a and b were derived from the
283 previously reported values (4), which were estimated to minimize residual sum of the square
284 (RSS) between $b k_7^a$ and $k_4 k_5$ in all subjects. (B) Scatter plots for $a \log k_7 + \log b$ versus
285 $\log k_4 k_5$ in NGT, IGT, and T2DM subjects (Eq (1)). The parameters a and b were derived
286 from the previously reported values (4).

287

288

289 **Figure S2. Relation between insulin-related parameters and blood glucose levels.**

290 (A) Scatter plot for $\log k_7 + a_a \log \text{PG120} + b_a$ versus $\log k_4 k_5$. Each point corresponds to
291 the values for a single subject. Green circles, red crosses, and blue squares indicate NGT,
292 IGT, and T2DM subjects, respectively. r is Pearson's correlation coefficient, and the value in
293 the parenthesis is 95% confidence interval. The parameters a_a and b_a were estimated to
294 minimize residual sum of the square (RSS) between $\log k_7 + a_a \log \text{PG120} + b_a$ and
295 $\log k_4 k_5$ in all subjects. (B) Scatter plots for $\log k_7 + a \log \text{PG120} + b$ versus $\log k_4 k_5$ in
296 NGT, IGT, and T2DM subjects. The parameters a_n and b_n , a_i and b_i , and a_t and b_t were
297 estimated to minimize RSS between $\log k_7 + a \log \text{PG120} + b$ and $\log k_4 k_5$ in NGT, IGT,
298 and T2DM subjects, respectively. (C) Scatter plot for $3 \log k_7 + a_a \log \text{PG120} + b_a$ versus
299 $\log k_4 k_5$. The parameters a_a and b_a were estimated to minimize RSS between $3 \log k_7 +$
300 $a_a \log \text{PG120} + b_a$ and $\log k_4 k_5$ in all subjects. (D) Scatter plots for $3 \log k_7 +$
301 $a \log \text{PG120} + b$ versus $\log k_4 k_5$ in NGT, IGT, and T2DM subjects. The parameters a_n and
302 b_n , a_i and b_i , and a_t and b_t were estimated to minimize RSS between $3 \log k_7 +$
303 $a \log \text{PG120} + b$ and $\log k_4 k_5$ in NGT, IGT, and T2DM subjects, respectively. The indices
304 k_4 , k_5 , and k_7 , which correspond to insulin sensitivity, insulin secretion, and insulin
305 clearance, respectively, were calculated by a previously described method (4). NGT, normal
306 glucose tolerance; IGT, impaired glucose tolerance; T2DM, type 2 diabetes mellitus; PG120,
307 plasma glucose concentration at 120 min during the OGTT.

308

309

310 **Figure S3. Comparison of the lines estimated by Eq (2) or Eq (3) in NGT, IGT, and**
 311 **T2DM.**

312 (A) Estimated slopes of Eq (2) by the standardized major axis test. (B) Estimated slopes of
 313 Eq (3) by the standardized major axis test. Bars indicate 95% confidence intervals. The P
 314 value is for testing the hypothesis of no difference among groups. NGT, normal glucose
 315 tolerance; IGT, impaired glucose tolerance; T2DM, type 2 diabetes mellitus.

316

317

318

319 **Figure S4. Relation between insulin-related parameters and blood glucose levels.**

320 (A) Scatter plot for $a_a \log \text{PG120} + b_a$ versus $\log k_{\text{sen}} k_{\text{sec}}$ (Eq (2)). Each point corresponds
321 to the values for a single subject. Green circles, red crosses, and blue squares indicate NGT,
322 IGT, and T2DM subjects, respectively. r is Pearson's correlation coefficient, and the value in
323 the parenthesis is 95% confidence interval. The parameters a_a and b_a were estimated to
324 minimize RSS between $a_a \log \text{PG120} + b_a$ and $\log k_{\text{sen}} k_{\text{sec}}$ in all subjects. (B) Scatter plots
325 for $a \log \text{PG120} + b$ versus $\log k_{\text{sen}} k_{\text{sec}}$ in NGT, IGT, and T2DM subjects (Eq (2)). The
326 parameters a_n and b_n , a_i and b_i , and a_t and b_t were estimated to minimize RSS between
327 $a \log \text{PG120} + b$ and $\log k_{\text{sen}} k_{\text{sec}}$ in NGT, IGT, and T2DM subjects, respectively. (C)
328 Scatter plot for $2 \log k_{\text{cle}} + a_a \log \text{PG120} + b_a$ versus $\log k_{\text{sen}} k_{\text{sec}}$ (Eq (3)). The parameters
329 a_a and b_a were estimated to minimize RSS between $2 \log k_{\text{cle}} + a_a \log \text{PG120} + b_a$ and
330 $\log k_{\text{sen}} k_{\text{sec}}$ in all subjects. (D) Scatter plots for $2 \log k_{\text{cle}} + a \log \text{PG120} + b$ versus
331 $\log k_{\text{sen}} k_{\text{sec}}$ in NGT, IGT, and T2DM subjects (Eq (3)). The parameters a_n and b_n , a_i and
332 b_i , and a_t and b_t were estimated to minimize RSS between $2 \log k_{\text{cle}} + a \log \text{PG120} + b$ and
333 $\log k_{\text{sen}} k_{\text{sec}}$ in NGT, IGT, and T2DM subjects, respectively. The indices k_{sen} , k_{sec} , and k_{cle} ,
334 correspond to insulin sensitivity, insulin secretion, and insulin clearance, respectively
335 (Appendix 1), and PG120 is the plasma glucose concentration at 120 min during an OGTT.
336
337

338

339 **Figure S5. DI_{cle} , disposition index and insulin clearance.**

340 Box plots of $k_{sen} k_{sec} / k_{cle}^2$, $k_{sen} k_{sec}$, and k_{cle}^2 in NGT, IGT, and T2DM subjects,

341 respectively. The indices k_{sen} , k_{sec} , and k_{cle} correspond to insulin sensitivity, insulin

342 secretion, and insulin clearance (Appendix 1), respectively. The indices $k_{sen} k_{sec} / k_{cle}^2$ and

343 $k_{sen} k_{sec}$ correspond to DI_{cle} and disposition index, respectively. Each point corresponds to

344 the value for a single subject. The boxes denote the median and upper and lower quartiles. P

345 values were determined by the Steel-Dwass test.

346

347

348 **Figure S6. Relation between parameters estimated from a hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic**
349 **clamp alone and those estimated from both hyperglycemic and hyperinsulinemic-**
350 **euglycemic clamps.**

351 (A) Model diagram of the previously described mathematical model (4) (CC-BY 4.0 license).

352 The letters within the circle indicate the variables of the model, the arrows denote the fluxes,

353 and the lines ending in circles or bars represent activation or inactivation, respectively. ϕ

354 indicates a fixed value. The variables G and I represent blood glucose and insulin

355 concentrations, respectively. The variable Y corresponds to the effective glucose
356 concentration for induction of variable X , which represents insulin secreted from pancreatic
357 β -cells. (B) Estimated parameters of the previously described model (4) (Fig. S6A) based on
358 a hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic clamp alone. The base of the logarithm is 10. (C) Spearman's
359 correlation coefficients. Bars indicate 95% confidence intervals. The parameters k_{4_full} ,
360 k_{5_full} , k_{7_full} , $k_5/k_7^2_full$, and $k_4k_5/k_7^2_full$ correspond to insulin sensitivity, insulin
361 secretion, insulin clearance, the ratio of insulin secretion to the square of insulin clearance,
362 and DI_{cle} estimated from both hyperglycemic and hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic clamps by
363 the previously described mathematical model (4) (Fig. S6A). The parameters k_{4_ins} , k_{5_ins} ,
364 k_{7_ins} , $k_5/k_7^2_ins$, and $k_4k_5/k_7^2_ins$ correspond to insulin sensitivity, insulin secretion,
365 insulin clearance, the ratio of insulin secretion to the square of insulin clearance, and DI_{cle}
366 estimated from the hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic clamp alone by the previously described
367 mathematical model (4) (Fig. S6A).

368

369

370 **Figure S7. Relation between DI_{cle} estimated from a hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic clamp**
 371 **alone and that estimated from both hyperglycemic and hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic**
 372 **clamps.**

373 (A) Scatter plot for $\log k_4 k_5 / k_7^2_{ins}$ versus $\log k_4 k_5 / k_7^2_{full}$. The parameters

374 $k_4 k_5 / k_7^2_{ins}$ and $k_4 k_5 / k_7^2_{full}$ correspond to DI_{cle} estimated from the hyperinsulinemic-

375 euglycemic clamp alone and DI_{cle} estimated from both hyperglycemic and hyperinsulinemic-

376 euglycemic clamps by the previously described mathematical model (4) (Fig. S6A),

377 respectively. Each point corresponds to the values for a single subject, with green circles, red

378 crosses, and blue squares indicating NGT, IGT, and T2DM subjects, respectively. r is

379 Spearman's correlation coefficient, and the value in the parenthesis is 95% confidence

380 interval. (B) Scatter plot for $\log k_{m4} k_{m5} / k_{m7}^2_{ins}$ versus $\log k_4 k_5 / k_7^2_{full}$. The parameters

381 $k_{m4} k_{m5} / k_{m7}^2_{ins}$ and $k_4 k_5 / k_7^2_{full}$ correspond to DI_{cle} estimated from the

382 hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic clamp alone by the modified model (Fig. 3A) and that

383 estimated from the hyperglycemic and hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic clamps by the

384 previously described mathematical model (4) (Fig. S6A), respectively. NGT, normal glucose

385 tolerance; IGT, impaired glucose tolerance; T2DM, type 2 diabetes mellitus.

386

387

388 **Figure S8. Relation between parameters estimated from both hyperglycemic and**
 389 **hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic clamps by a previously described model and those**
 390 **estimated by a modified model.**

391 Scatter plot for $\log k_{4_full}$ versus $\log k_{m4_full}$ (A), $\log k_{5_full}$ versus $\log k_{m5_full}$ (B), and
 392 $\log k_{7_full}$ versus $\log k_{m7_full}$ (C). The parameters k_{4_full} , k_{5_full} and k_{7_full} correspond to
 393 insulin sensitivity, insulin secretion, and insulin clearance estimated from both hyperglycemic
 394 and hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic clamps by the previously described mathematical model
 395 (4), respectively. The parameters k_{m4_full} , k_{m5_full} and k_{m7_full} correspond to insulin
 396 sensitivity, insulin secretion, and insulin clearance estimated from the hyperglycemic and
 397 hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic clamps by the modified mathematical model (Fig. 3A),
 398 respectively. Each point corresponds to the values for a single subject, with green circles, red
 399 crosses, and blue squares indicating NGT, IGT, and T2DM subjects, respectively. r is
 400 Spearman's correlation coefficient, and the value in the parenthesis is 95% confidence
 401 interval. NGT, normal glucose tolerance; IGT, impaired glucose tolerance; T2DM, type 2
 402 diabetes mellitus.

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406 **Figure S9. Relation between DI_{cle} estimated from a hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic clamp**
 407 **alone and that estimated from both hyperglycemic and hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic**
 408 **clamps.**

409 Scatter plot for $\log k_{sen} k_{sec} / k_{cle}^2_{Cpep}$ versus $\log k_4 k_5 / k_7^2_{full}$. The parameters
 410 $k_{sen} k_{sec} / k_{cle}^2_{Cpep}$ and $k_4 k_5 / k_7^2_{full}$ correspond to DI_{cle} analytically estimated from the
 411 hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic clamp alone by the serum C-peptide concentration (Appendix
 412 1) and that estimated from both hyperglycemic and hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic clamps by
 413 the previously described mathematical model (4) (Fig. S6A), respectively. Each point
 414 corresponds to the values for a single subject, with green circles, red crosses, and blue
 415 squares indicating NGT, IGT, and T2DM subjects, respectively. r is Spearman's correlation
 416 coefficient, and the value in the parenthesis is 95% confidence interval.

417

418

419 **Figure S10. Relation between DI_{cle} estimated from both hyperglycemic and**
 420 **hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic clamps and that estimated from an oral glucose tolerance**
 421 **test or a fasting blood test.**

422 Scatter plot for $\log k_4 k_5 / k_7^2_{full}$ versus $\log k_{sen} k_{sec} / k_{cle}^2_{OGTT}$ (A) or $\log k_{sen} k_{sec} /$
 423 $k_{cle}^2_{fast}$ (B). The parameters $k_4 k_5 / k_7^2_{full}$, $k_{sen} k_{sec} / k_{cle}^2_{OGTT}$, and $k_{sen} k_{sec} / k_{cle}^2_{fast}$
 424 correspond to DI_{cle} estimated from both hyperglycemic and hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic
 425 clamps, that estimated from OGTT, and that estimated from a fasting blood test (Appendix
 426 8), respectively. Each point corresponds to the values for a single subject, with green circles,
 427 red crosses, and blue squares indicating NGT, IGT, and T2DM subjects, respectively. r is
 428 Spearman's correlation coefficient, and the value in the parenthesis is 95% confidence
 429 interval.

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